

Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean

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Pre-Operational Data Collection Pipeline

D4.2 EDITO-Infra

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List of abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
ARCO	Analysis Ready Cloud Optimized
B2B	Business to Business
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DANUBIUS-RI	International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems
DCC-OP	Decade Collaborative Centre for Ocean Prediction
DCO	Data Computing Orchestrator
DDD	Domain-Driven Design
DestinE	Destination Earth
DIAS	Data Information and Access services. Funded by Copernicus.
DITTO	Digital Twins of the Ocean
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DOF	Digital Ocean Forum
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDITO-Infra	EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean
EMBRC	The European Marine Biological Resource Centre
EMD	European Maritime Day
EMODnet	European Marine Observation & Data Network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ESA	European Space Agency
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract Transform Load
EU DTO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EUMETSAT	The European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EURO ARGO	European Research Infrastructure Consortium for Observing the Ocean
EUROGEO	Europe's part of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO)
EuroHPC Joint Undertaking	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FSOI	G7 Future of the Seas and Oceans Initiative
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2020	EU's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)
HE	EU's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027)
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JERICO	Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MOi	Mercator Ocean International
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
R&I	Research and Innovation

RI	Research Infrastructure
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SG	Stakeholder Groups
SIMPL	Simpl is an open source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOA Model	Service-oriented architecture Model
STAC	Spatial Temporal Asset Catalog
TA	Target Audience
TWG	Technical Working Group
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WEKEO	EU Copernicus DIAS reference service for environmental data, virtual processing environments and skilled user support
WiS	Web Information System

1. About EDITO-Infra and its pre-operational data collection pipeline

1.1 Overall aim of EDITO-Infra

The **European Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO)**, conceived as a public good and service, is a main deliverable of the Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Seas by 2030', and of its Digital Ocean Knowledge System in particular. It has as an objective to make ocean knowledge readily available, and actionable, to be used by researchers, public authorities, the private sector and citizens, to support their decision-making with fit-for-purpose and user-specific tools based on 'what-if scenarios'. The EU DTO will enable all the ocean actors to become partners in knowledge generation and its use for the pursuit of a healthy and productive ocean.

The main aim of the **“EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO-Infra)”** project is to build the **EU public infrastructure backbone** for the **EU DTO**. This has been done by upgrading, combining, and integrating key service components of the existing EU ocean observing, monitoring and data programmes, namely **“Copernicus Marine Service”** and the **“European Marine Observation & Data Network (EMODnet)”** into a **single digital framework**. In that context, EDITO-Infra is both the name of the project and the name of the platform that has been deployed (see <https://dive.edito.eu>).

The screenshot displays the EDITO Platform website. The main heading is "European Digital Twin Ocean Core Infrastructure". Below this, it states "Explore and share ocean data, models and services in an open and collaborative way". The page features three main action cards: "Learn about the ocean data science" (with a "Browse our tutorials" button), "Design and run digital twin ocean applications with your favorite tools" (with a "Discover the Datalab" button), and "Explore oceanographic data" (with "Explore data" and "Integrate data" buttons). A circular graphic on the right shows a globe surrounded by various scientific domains: Oceanography, Marine Special Economic Zones, Biogeotechnology, and Physical Oceanography. At the bottom, a "FEATURES" section lists three capabilities: "EXPLORE" (Use the European Digital Twin Ocean, Open without account), "CREATE" (Build your external third-party components, Open to beta-testers), and "CONTRIBUTE" (Add data, processes, services and tutorials, Open to privileged beta-testers). Each feature has a green checkmark indicating its status.

Figure 1: The first version of the EDITO-Infra platform

1.2 Purpose & scope of EDITO-Infra pre-operational data collection pipeline

This document outlines the **pre-operational data collection pipeline** for the EDITO-Infra project. It serves as a high-level overview of the processes involved in collecting and transforming data into the **ARCO** format, highlighting the services and tools currently in use. While this document does not aim to delve into extensive technical details, as that falls outside its scope, all relevant technical specifics are available in the associated code repositories available on <https://github.com/edito-infra>.

2. Pre-operational data collection pipeline

2.1 General overview

We have designed, developed, and implemented an automated pipeline to populate the EDITO Data Lake and a SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC), ensuring close alignment with the CMEMs STAC specification.

The EDITO Data Lake serves as a centralized repository for storing, managing, and providing access to large volumes of diverse data, currently including datasets from EMODnet and CMEMS.

The Data Lake consists of two primary components: **storage** and **cataloging**. The **storage** is based on MinIO technology, which provides a scalable, high-performance platform to host all data and assets. Connected to the storage is the **catalog**, which allows users to discover, search, and access the stored data efficiently.

Storage: S3-Compatible Object Store

At the heart of the data storage solution is MinIO, a distributed object storage system that is fully compatible with the Amazon S3 API. This compatibility ensures seamless integration with various tools, services, and frameworks already tailored to work with S3-based systems. MinIO is particularly well-suited for handling the very big datasets typical in satellite, marine and climate-related applications due to its scalability, fault tolerance, and support for high-throughput operations. The use of object storage enables the data to be stored as discrete objects, making it easier to manage, replicate, and access datasets flexibly and cost-effectively. This foundation ensures a robust and reliable infrastructure for hosting data assets.

Catalog: STAC Specification

The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) is a widely recognized, community-driven standard for organizing and sharing geospatial data. The catalog acts as an index to the data, enabling users to discover datasets based on spatial, temporal, and thematic parameters. By adopting the STAC specification, we ensure interoperability with existing geospatial data systems and tools (e.g. OGC, GeoNetwork, GeoServer,...). The catalog includes standardized metadata descriptions, providing details such as the dataset's spatial and temporal extent, asset links, and key properties. This structure aligns with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) by enhancing data discoverability and usability for a wide range of users, including researchers, developers, and policymakers.

Data Processing and Standardization

To populate the Data Lake, we developed a programmatic process (an ETL pipeline) for transferring data resources. In addition to simply synchronizing the data into the storage, we applied transformations to align the datasets with the ARCO format where possible. ARCO formats are designed to make the best use of the high-speed data transfer properties of the S3 storage technology, this particularly useful for big datasets. The ARCO transformation process involved standardizing parameter names to adhere to common vocabularies, such as the Climate and Forecast (CF) conventions or the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) naming schemes. These standardizations improve interoperability and consistency across datasets.

In certain cases, we opted to retain parameter names as they were originally provided, especially when those names align with how end-users are most likely to search for or utilize the data. This decision ensures compliance with FAIR principles, prioritizing accessibility and usability while maintaining the scientific integrity of the datasets.

2.2 Input components

MetaGIS

One of the key components for managing layers in the EDITO Data Lake is **MetaGIS**, a tool specifically developed to handle technical metadata of geospatial layers. MetaGIS has been further enhanced to manage the layers ingested into the EDITO Data Lake. It enables users to define parameter names, specify which layers should undergo ARCO transformation, determine their placement within the hierarchical STAC catalog, and more.

The tool provides a streamlined way to update datasets and metadata without requiring direct interaction with the code. Its graphical user interface makes it accessible to both technical and non-technical users, allowing for efficient dataset management when needed. While MetaGIS has some limitations, which are discussed in Chapter 3 (Challenges and Opportunities Ahead), it fully meets the requirements of the current project phase.

Figure 2: MetaGIS Geospatial management tool

Python script: Catalog Services for the Web

In addition to MetaGIS, which allows for overriding parameter names and locations within the STAC catalog, a Python script has been developed to parse a CSW (Catalog Service for the Web) URL.

The key advantage of this approach is its ability to ingest a full catalog automatically without manual intervention. One advantage of this approach is that all updates are managed by the CSW provider, ensuring consistency and smooth integration of changes into the EDITO Data Lake. The script provides a seamless machine-to-machine ingestion process and has been successfully used to import the entire EMODnet catalog into the EDITO Data Lake.

The code is available here: <https://github.com/EDITO-Infra/csw-to-stac>

Python script: ERDDAP

A script has been developed to seamlessly parse data from ERDDAP servers. This fully automated, machine-to-machine process ensures efficient data ingestion into the EDITO Data Lake while preserving the metadata provided by ERDDAP.

The code is available here: https://github.com/EDITO-Infra/edito-pipeline/blob/main/src/update_metagis_layers/erddap_metagis.py

2.3 Processing components

The various input components feeding into the ingestion process are complemented by a range of tools, processes, and services designed to transform datasets as needed. These transformations focus on both ARCO format conversion and improving metadata for enhanced user experience and findability.

Transformation Tools and Processes

Tools have been developed to convert traditional geospatial data into ARCO formats, standardizing formats, and resolutions for modern geospatial workflows. Written in Python, these tools leverage open-source technologies, libraries, and frameworks to ensure interoperability.

Gridded datasets are transformed into (geo)ZARR format, an open, efficient format optimized for storing large multidimensional arrays. ZARR supports chunked, compressed, and distributed data storage, making it highly efficient for large-scale geospatial data. Its compatibility with parallel processing tools enhances data access and storage, particularly in cloud environments. The "geo" variant extends ZARR to better handle geospatial data, such as raster datasets, in ways that are optimized for spatial analysis and visualization.

Vector datasets, such as shapefiles, are converted into Parquet format, a columnar storage format designed for large-scale data processing. Parquet offers superior data compression and performance, enabling faster queries and reducing storage requirements. This format is widely used in big data frameworks like Apache Spark and Hadoop, streamlining data access and processing. The geo-variant ensures that geospatial data types, like geometries and spatial indexing, are handled effectively.

Both (geo)ZARR and (geo)Parquet file formats are specifications developed and maintained by the **Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)**, a global organization dedicated to advancing open standards for geospatial and location-based data. The OGC's role is to ensure interoperability and standardization across geospatial technologies, promoting the seamless exchange of data and services within the geospatial community.

Additionally, while vector datasets are typically transformed into Parquet, some are instead converted into grid formats for easier integration with geospatial tools and systems. These gridded datasets are available in the catalog, and the transformation services are accessible on the platform, allowing end-users to convert their datasets to grids as needed.

2.4 Output components

After the data processing is complete, the generated files are pushed to the object store using the **MinIO API**, which facilitates the uploading of files to the appropriate **bucket** in the storage system. The MinIO API is fully compatible with **Amazon S3** commands, providing a seamless way to interact with S3-like object storage services. By using **S3 commands** (S3cmd, AWS CLI, or SDKs), files can be uploaded, downloaded, listed, and managed in the object store efficiently.

Along with file uploads, the STAC catalog is also updated as part of the pipeline process. To ensure data integrity, we maintain a development environment alongside the production environment. This setup allows all updates or additions to dataset metadata to be thoroughly reviewed before being reflected in the operational catalog. The development version acts as a staging area for final quality control checks, helping to prevent unintended modifications or errors from reaching production. This clear separation between development and production is essential for maintaining the reliability and accuracy of the operational system, ensuring that only validated changes are deployed.

Currently, this setup allows for a controlled and secure update process, minimizing the risk of introducing unwanted changes into the live environment. By requiring changes to be pushed from the development version to production, it provides an additional layer of verification and quality assurance before the data becomes publicly accessible or operational.

The code is available here: <https://github.com/EDITO-Infra/edito-pipeline>

2.5 Schematic overview of the pipeline

Fig 3. Schematic Overview of the current pipeline

3. Challenges Ahead

3.1 Harmonizing Third-Party Data with the EDITO Ecosystem

In developing the pipeline for ingesting EMODnet and CMEMS data into the EDITO data lake, considerable progress has been made. However, challenges remain, particularly in optimizing data synchronization processes. Currently, periodic data ingestion is required to maintain synchronization. Exploring more efficient methods - such as real-time change detection or implementing a fragmental update system - could enhance operational efficiency.

Additionally, incorporating third-party data presents its own complexities, including variability in formats, metadata standards, and update frequencies. Ensuring that all ingested datasets align with a unified STAC catalogue requires rigorous validation, transformation workflows, and adherence to a common schema. As we move toward the next phase of EDITO, establishing clear technical guidelines for integrating other external sources outside EMODnet and CMEMS (i.e. from several marine HE projects) will be essential to maintaining consistency, interoperability, and discoverability across the data lake.

As mentioned in previous section, MetaGIS is a geospatial management tool used by VLIZ to oversee multiple data systems and has been further adapted to meet the needs of EDITO.

We plan to improve the management of the EDITO data lake by enabling third-party access, minimizing manual change requests, and implementing machine-to-machine connectivity for greater efficiency. Additionally, we're enhancing capabilities by introducing support for layers with multiple assets, a feature not yet available in MetaGIS.